

THE ROLE OF MOBILE APPLICATIONS IN IMPROVING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING COMPETENCY

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the role of mobile applications in teaching the Russian language in non-philological universities. The author provides examples and analyzes them, giving their pros and cons.

The development of pedagogy in the XXI century is closely related to technological progress and is characterized by the widespread use of information and communication technologies. The use of Internet resources has become an integral part of teaching any subject, and in the process of learning a foreign language - the educational process. The World Wide Web offers unlimited opportunities to use authentic materials from other cultures.

The term "mobile learning" (mobile learning - M-learning) refers to the process of teaching and using mobile and portable IT devices such as PDAs, mobile phones and tablet computers.

Mobile education is closely related to electronic and distance education, their difference is the use of mobile devices, in which students can access their Russian language skills anywhere and anytime (on the basis of synchronous and asynchronous means of communication). It is possible to develop and improve their skills, as well as to form socio-cultural and intercultural competence to use the Russian language as a means of communication in the social sphere.

Smartphones are one of the most common mobile devices among young people. According to statistics, the number of smartphone users is increasing every year, and their popularity among young people cannot be overestimated.

Therefore, it is impossible to ignore mobile devices in Russian language classes. Taking this into account, the question arises as to how rationally and effectively mobile phones, smartphones and tablets can be used in the classroom. However, despite the presence of mobile phones among pupils and students, mobile learning is underutilized in the learning process. Self-directed learning, flexibility and instant information are the hallmarks of mobile learning.

In the process of learning Russian, portable and mobile devices are used not only for

receiving and processing information, but also for continuous learning, for example, using electronic dictionaries, books, audio and video of other language learning tools. provide with

Modernization of the educational process requires the Russian language teacher to implement innovative pedagogical technologies. In recent years, due to the gradual introduction of mobile technologies into the educational environment, approaches to teaching the Russian language have changed significantly, which, combined with the unlimited possibilities of the World Wide Web, has led to the emergence of mobile education. was the basis for it. There are several definitions of the term m-learning - "mobile education".

Mobile education is the transfer of knowledge to a mobile device (phone or laptop) using WAP or GPRS technologies (that is, the main thing is access to the Internet);

- mobile education - technologies that allow organizing the educational process using mobile communication tools, for example, mobile phones and communicators (the ability to access the Internet is not the main thing here);

- Mobile education is a learning process that is a type of distance education, for its implementation, knowledge is transferred to personal devices (laptop, PDA or mobile phone). Information transfer methods can be different.

The mobile phone and its functionality allow you to organize training using customized e-textbooks, training courses and specialized types of files with training information - training manuals directly ri is developed for mobile phone platforms.

The following apps are available for additional language practice:

1. Russian for the WORLD applications offer a large selection for smartphones. Apps can be viewed on the Council's website and downloaded via Google Play, Apple's AppStore.

The Russian Grammar's Word Challenge app stands out - it's a great way to improve your grammar.

2. Quizlet is a free ad-free app that has many ready-made lessons on various topics such as foreign languages for communication, business language, different foreign languages for travel, idioms and phrases. The application allows you to create your own modules with vocabulary on various topics.

3. Real Language – Offers a wide range of applications for different levels of real English, Russian and other languages – business and conversational English for beginner, intermediate and advanced levels. Each of the apps contains 20 to 100 lessons that focus on specific areas of grammar and vocabulary.

4. Duolingo is free, ad-free and very effective. The learning process in Duolingo is built around playing and achieving. The course consists of lessons, each of which contains different tasks. Tasks are offered to teach reading, translation, pronunciation and spelling.

Lingua Leo – Lingualeo is a free program for memorizing words. We recommend that students use this app to memorize professional vocabulary, as they can create their own dictionaries where they can enter words they need to learn or repeat.

Four types of teaching are possible in this application: word translation, translation-word, word constructor, listening. In the first case, you need to choose a suitable translation for the word from the proposed ones, in the second - the same, on the contrary. Constructor - knowing the translation, you need to assemble the English word from the letters.

5. Cahoot! educational application (in English and Russian) that allows you to conduct tests, quizzes and discussions in cooperative learning mode completely free of charge.

In addition, popular mobile applications that students use every day can also be used to learn foreign languages.

For students with a high level of preparation, we suggest using WhatsApp, Viber, VKontakte to exchange messages in Russian and complete various tasks. A group or conversation is created for a certain number of students, where they can share ideas and projects.

You can, for example, use the following task types:

- send students a short article or podcast on a lesson topic and ask them to send back an audio file summarizing the article in their own words or content;
- students can submit photos or images with captions or captions that demonstrate the use of new professional vocabulary;
- post a new topic each week and invite students to post images and quotes about it.

Thus, the use of mobile applications in teaching a foreign language, that is, the Russian language, in our opinion, helps to increase the enthusiasm of students, creates a personal professionally oriented space for the student, develops independent learning skills and continuous lifelong learning, forms the ability to acquire knowledge. In addition, by equipping students with easy-to-use learning tools on the go, we enable them to integrate self-study into their busy lives, accelerate learning and ensure better results.

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